

Crop management

Influence of planting dates on productivity of traditional scented rice varieties

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To exploit the full yield potential of traditional scented rice varieties, it is necessary to determine their optimum planting time for specific locations. A field experiment was conducted during the 1993 and 1994 wet seasons using a split-plot design with four dates of planting as main plot treatments and three varieties of traditional Basmati as subplot treatments, replicated four times.

Soil at the experimental site was sandy loam, low in organic C (0.41%), low in available P (7.7 kg ha⁻¹), and medium in K (178.5 kg ha⁻¹) with pH 7.8. The crop was fertilized with 60, 13.2, and 24.9 kg of N, P, and K ha⁻¹, respectively of which 50% N, full P, and K along with 5.8 kg Zn ha⁻¹ were applied uniformly as basal dressing and incorporated. The other 50% N was applied in two equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. Seedlings (21 d old) were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings hill⁻¹.

Dates of planting influenced the grain yield of Basmati rice significantly during both years of study (see table). The highest mean grain yield was recorded from the 1 Jul planting date and did not differ significantly from the 16 Jul planting, but yield differed from that of 31 Jul and 16 Aug. A linear reduction in grain yield with every 15-d delay in planting was recorded from 1 Jul (4.1 t ha⁻¹) to 16 Aug (2.5 t ha⁻¹). The percent reduction in grain yield averaged over 2 yr was 11.8, 20.8, and 37.4%, respectively, for 16 Jul, 31 Jul, and 16 Aug as compared with the grain yield of the 1 Jul planting. In yield-contributing characters, panicle weight differed significantly during both years while panicles m⁻² differed only during

1994. The maximum panicles m⁻² were recorded for the 1 Jul planting, whereas panicle weight remained the same for the 1 Jul and 16 Jul plantings. The interaction between planting dates × varieties was not significant.

The test varieties did not differ significantly among themselves in grain yield. Basmati 370 had a slightly higher grain yield (3.40 t ha⁻¹), followed by Taraori Basmati (3.38 t ha⁻¹). Basmati 370 also had the highest average

panicles m⁻² (387 m⁻²) while Taraori Basmati had the highest average panicle weight (1.67 g panicle⁻¹).

Results indicated that Basmati 370 could be used for early planting whereas Ranveer Basmati could be used for delayed planting. The higher grain yield of such traditional scented rice varieties could be achieved by transplanting them during the first fortnight of July in the western part of Uttar Pradesh. ■

Grain yield and yield-contributing characters of traditional scented rice varieties under different planting dates. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1993-94 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Panicles m ⁻² (no.)			Panicle weight(g)		
	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	Mean
<i>Planting date</i>									
1 Jul	4.2	3.9	4.1	406	358	382	1.74	1.68	1.71
16 Jul	3.6	3.5	3.6	369	345	357	1.71	1.70	1.71
31 Jul	3.3	3.1	3.2	385	330	358	1.67	1.59	1.63
16 Aug	2.8	2.3	2.5	378	309	344	1.62	1.55	1.59
CD (5%)	0.9	0.7	-	ns	15	-	0.03	0.05	-
<i>Variety</i>									
Basmati 370	3.5	3.3	3.4	409	365	387	1.64	1.60	1.62
Ranveer Basmati	3.5	3.1	3.3	383	355	369	1.67	1.52	1.60
Taraori Basmati	3.5	3.2	3.4	361	360	361	1.73	1.61	1.67
CD (5%)	ns	ns	-	ns	9	-	0.02	0.06	0

Seedling vigor affects stand establishment and performance of flood-prone lowland rice

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We conducted a field experiment at Cuttack, India, during 1993 using three long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties of different plant heights. Vegetative tillers were transplanted from conventional nursery seedbeds unfertilized or with N fertilization (100 kg N ha⁻¹ at sowing). Their performance was compared with that of sowings at 400 kg N ha⁻¹ in a nursery seedbed in a relatively upland field and 80 kg N ha⁻¹ in a lowland field, from where about 100 tillers m⁻² were up-

rooted and transplanted. Seedlings and vegetative tillers (45 d old) were transplanted into 8 cm of water at 20 × 15-cm spacing of 2-3 hill⁻¹ in a randomized block design with three replications and fertilized with a basal dose of 40 kg N ha⁻¹, 8.7 kg P ha⁻¹, and 16.7 kg K ha⁻¹.

Vigor depended on variety and type of seedling (see table). Fertilizer N application in the seedbed improved height and dry weight compared with unfertilized seedlings.

Two floods occurred within the month of transplanting (see figure). The taller and heavier plants were well established when subjected to 54 cm of water 4 d after transplanting. Plants raised from nursery seedlings suffered the greatest damage. Unfertilized seed-

lings (27-34 cm height) remained completely under water for nearly a week, whereas the top 2-3 leaves of fertilized seedlings were above water. The second flood killed most of the unfertilized seedlings. The mean grain yields of all rice varieties were similar, but crops raised from vegetative tillers

yielded best. Panicle number in the vegetative propagated crop was 112-132 m⁻² and their weight was 3.39-3.63 g, leading to a grain yield of more than 4 t ha⁻¹. Nursery seedlings had very low yields and poor crop stand even with good panicle weight (2.70-3.32 g) because the flood reduced panicle num-

ber (61-88%) and tillers. Straw yield was highest with Matangini, and its nursery seedlings were also significantly better than those of Utkalprabha and Gayatri.

Seedling height and dry weight at transplanting determine survivability, crop stand, and productivity under flood-prone conditions. Suitable varieties can be obtained either by uprooting vegetative tillers from a field-grown crop or from a conventional nursery seedbed raised using relatively low seed density and basal N fertilization. ■

Effect of seedling vigor on growth and yield attributes of rice varieties under flood-prone conditions. Cuttack, India. 1993.

Treatment	Seedling vigor ^a		Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Height (cm)	Dry weight (g seedling ⁻¹)					
Gayatri (semidwarf)							
Unfertilized seedlings	27	0.08	74	15	2.89	0.2	0.3
Fertilized seedlings	33	0.15	93	28	3.30	0.9	1.5
Vegetative tillers	71	0.86	106	124	3.63	4.1	5.5
Utkalprabha (semi-tall)							
Unfertilized seedlings	32	0.08	105	22	3.18	0.4	0.8
Fertilized seedlings	56	0.18	107	34	3.32	0.7	1.5
Vegetative tillers	71	0.79	136	133	3.59	4.3	6.2
Matangini (tall)							
Unfertilized seedlings	34	0.17	107	31	2.70	0.7	1.4
Fertilized seedlings	57	0.22	114	43	2.98	1.3	2.3
Vegetative tillers	98	1.25	164	112	3.39	4.1	7.6
CD (0.05)							
Varieties			6	ns	0.18	ns	0.35
Kind of seedlings			6	8	0.18	0.33	0.35
Varieties × kind of seedlings			6	13	ns	ns	0.61
CV (%)			3.2	12.9	5.5	17.7	11.6

^aBased on mean of 25 seedlings.

Water depth (cm)

Flooding patterns during the growth period of rice. Cuttack, India. 1993.

Integrated pest management

A survey of rice constraints in the Mekong Delta

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A survey was conducted in three rice-cropping seasons of 1996 in the Can Tho Province of Vietnam. The sample consisted of 73 fields distributed over these successive seasons (20, 32, and 21 fields) and four villages. The Survey Portfolio of the Rice Research Prioritization Project supported by the Rockefeller Foundation was used.

Analysis of variance was carried out on individual injuries attributable to

pests for the three seasons (see table). Leaf folder (LF), deadhearts (DH), and leaf blast (LB) injuries were higher in winter-spring; weed infestation (above the rice crop canopy WA) and sheath rot (ShR) injuries were higher in summer; and brown spot (BS) and bacterial blight (BLB) injuries were higher in autumn. Brown planthopper (BPH) populations were higher in winter-spring, although remaining at low levels. Injury due to red stripe syndrome (RS) was also highest in winter-spring, and next highest in summer.

Analysis of variance was likewise conducted on individual injuries for various levels of cropping practices. We found numerical, but not significant effects, of fertilizer inputs on levels of

injuries, except for sheath blight (ShB) ($P < 0.01$, increase with fertilizer application) and weed infestation below the rice crop (WB, $P = 0.02$, decrease with fertilizer application). No numerical trends, nor significant differences, were found to suggest a link between fertilizer input and BS or RS. Some injuries differed ($P < 0.05$) in intensity depending on location (village): WB, DH, BS, and NB, reflecting the influence of a number of possible factors (e.g., soil characteristics, varieties, crop husbandry). No significant insecticide effects on any injury attributable to insects were found except one, BPH, where injury was significantly ($P = 0.039$) increased when insecticide was used. No significant effect of fungicide on